

Myanmar Payment Union: Standardized Services for All Kind of Payments in Myanmar

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Abstract: *This paper investigates the role of Myanmar Payment Union (MPU) in all digital payment services. As small and medium businesses, and consumers demand rises, the need for more advanced digital payments solutions is demanding. The research analyses how all-in-one standardized solutions help solve all these problems and brings toward more seamless and effortless experiences for both users and merchants. With the emergence of MPU and banking services that are integrated into banking applications and MPU cards, the customers can now make transactions effortlessly from online shopping, bill payments and digital fixed deposit to Interbank Fund Transfer, and local and international remittance anytime anywhere. On top of that, the paper highlights the importance of MMQR by studying the technologies and services provided to achieve one universal Quick Response code for all kinds of scan payments. To add on, the graphs in this paper show the rapid progress from the year of introduction. Furthermore, the study observes limitations and suggests improvements, which are required to complete a more secure digital payment system in the future. The research also gives a different view of MPU services for rural areas, emphasizing the lower implementation rate in provincial areas compared to cities. By evaluating both advantages and disadvantages, this paper provides constructive feedback and valuable insight for both scholars and people from banking sectors.*

Keywords: Myanmar Quick Response (MMQR), Interbank Fund Transfer (IBFT), Digital Wallets (E-wallets).

I. INTRODUCTION

As the small and medium businesses are growing and shopping is becoming more popular, the demand for digital payments is skyrocketing. With the digital payments, you can pay the exact amount of money even for little and insignificant amounts. So, it is way better in most scenarios in purchasing things. As consumers' demand for accessing better digital services for both shopping online and paying with more efficient services at shopping at the physical store, electronic payment is becoming more demanding. There are three types of digital payments, namely, Myanmar Payment Union cards, Mobile banking apps, and Digital wallets(E-wallets).

Banking apps are now becoming advanced tools for both buying things and managing funds and assets from any part of the world where internet access is available.

The role of MPU cards come into play, providing Interbank Fund Transfer to the mobile banking apps. MPU cards are also available with MPU E-commerce services, enabling withdraw and purchase functions more conveniently. In contrast, MPU cards are not suitable for the type of person who does not have bank account but still wants to use digital payment services. So, E-wallets such as KBZ pay, CB pay and AYA pay are distributed to fulfil these needs. So, E-wallets take the first place in digital payment methods, followed by MPU cards in the second, and mobile banking apps in the final but with the most important banking services. However, recent studies proved that several E-wallets with different standards and individual accounts create confusion and inconveniences between sellers and consumers. Also, different MPU cards, issued by individual banks, cause errors and difficulties. To address these problems, this study aims to analyse three types of solutions that alleviate and solve all these unsynchronized problems. This study investigates how MPU, IBFT and MMQR standard provide seamless experiences for customer enabling smarter shopping with any types of digital E-wallets or MPU card.

On top of that, this research extends how these three standards achieve a straightforward online interbank transaction that can be created by users. MPU cards can be registered for E-commerce services to access these services. Also, the emergence of MPU new QR standard helps move digital banking to more modernized future. Money can be transferred to different E-wallets using standardized MMQR (e.g. From KBZ pay to AYA pay). So, these MPU essential services also drive revolutionary banking services that accelerate the role of mobile banking in businesses.

II. Literature Review

2.1 What is Payment System

A payment and settlement system in general is a framework to carry out smooth delivery of funds and/or securities between individuals, business, and financial institutions. It comprises a set of payment instruments, procedures, rules, and technical facilities used to implement clearing, transfer of funds and/or securities, and final settlement. Most payment systems nowadays are supported by IT infrastructures such as hardware, software, and communication networks.[2]

2.2 Legal Aspects of Payment and Settlement Systems

The Central Bank of Myanmar Law, Financial Institutions Law, and Anti-money Laundering Law are legal basis for operation and oversight of payment and settlement systems including participants. The Central Bank of Myanmar Law (2013) states developing efficient, fast, safe, and reliable national payment and settlement systems is one of the main responsibilities of the Central Bank of Myanmar (CBM). Financial Institution Law (2016) then emphasizes CBM is to formulate, adopt and monitor the implementation of a payment system policy of Myanmar. In line with these obligations, CBM has made policies, regulations and rules related to the payment and settlement systems considering globalization in economic activities and rapid progress in information technology.

The regulations are designed not only to provide safe, smooth, and efficient payment and settlement systems but to protect the interest of all parties involved in payment services. The CBM therefore has a mandate for issuing licenses to payment service providers and oversight of these institutions.

The CBM in the process of making policies considers mitigating risks and improving efficiency and safety of the payment and settlement systems, such as introduction of an RTGS (real time gross settlement) system for inter-bank transactions. As a result of our continuous efforts, dramatic improvement in payment system activities is being achieved in line with the increasing public needs for both cash and non-cash payment instruments.[1]

2.3 Myanmar Payment Union (MPU)

Myanmar Payment Union (MPU) is the national payment network of Myanmar. Established in 2011 under the guidance of the Central Bank of Myanmar, serving as the central switch that connects the nation's financial institutions, merchants, and consumers.

Myanmar Payment Union (MPU) is a Myanmar financial services corporation headquartered in Yangon, Myanmar. It provides bank card services and a major card scheme in Myanmar.

MPU was founded on 15 September 2011 with total of 16 members from both state- and privately-owned banks and expanded to 23 members as of 19 Jan 2017. When it first started, its purpose was to provide the ATM and POS (Point of Sale) switching services among the banks. MPU cards have been issued since 14 September 2012.

As a result, all bank card holders can withdraw and check their balances and remittances to and from their fund at any ATM at any of the participating banks. With the direction of the Central Bank of Myanmar, Myanmar Payment Union was organized on 15 September 2011 in Yangon by state owned and private banks. On 23 November 2012, Japan Credit Bureau (JCB) signed an agreement on the use of its payment system at the Myanmar Banks Association and CUP followed suit the next day.

Within this agreement holders of international bank cards with agreements with either JCB or CUP will be able to use them in the automatic teller machines of the member banks of the Myanmar Payment Union.[2]

2.4 ATM, POS and CARD switch by Myanmar Payment Union: MPU standards

Promoting cash-less economy to reduce burden of handling currency notes and to reduce the currency in circulation within the country, the CBM encourages financial institutions to issue debit/credit cards and to establish ATMs across the country through the Myanmar Payment Union network. Later, this network may be linked to ASEAN Payment Network (APN). Myanmar Payment Union (MPU) was organized by state owned and private banks in 2011.

The purpose of MPU is to provide the ATM and POS switching services among the banks. The use of MPU cards at ATM and POS has started on September 14, 2012. As a result, all bank card holders can withdraw and check their balance, remit their funds at any ATMs, and make payments at any POS terminals located nationwide and at e-commerce websites. CBM then permits international card schemes such as VISA, MasterCard and JCB doing credit and debit card business in Myanmar with the aim to promote cashless payment.[3]

2.5 Mobile Wallet

The advent of mobile phone technologies and digital currency allows to move the unbanked into formal financial sector in Myanmar. The CBM – using the momentum in rapid spread of mobile phones – established a framework and Mobile Financial Service regulations to enable Mobile Network Operators (MNO) operate mobile wallet services particularly for citizens who do not have access to banks.

The regulation guarantees customer protection and risk mitigations measures so that users can feel safe to make remittance their digital money nationwide. The CBM also leads and governs standardization of QR code payments for both merchant and customer present, which will enable interoperable payments across payment services.[3]

III.Methodology

3.1 MPU Foundation

Myanmar's economy is mostly cash-based. The first ATM cards were introduced in 1995, and credit cards were issued by private banks. However, after the financial crisis in Myanmar in 2003, private banks stopped issuing credit cards. After the reopening of Myanmar's economy in 2010, the banking and payment system changes are an important reform of the financial industry.

3.2. MPU Purpose

The priority is to convert the local cash-based payment system to an electronic payment system. The main purpose of forming the MPU is to act as a National Payment Switch (NPS) for all of Myanmar. To transition to cashless payment by cooperating in payment activities through electronic network among member banks and to connect with the international payment network in the future.

3.3 Conversion to public company

In July 2015, the MPU organization changed to a public company, and now there are (30) member banks. Among of 30 banks, 21 banks have issued debit cards and are installing ATMs and POS machines in the market

3.4 E-Commerce Services

The introduction of the E-commerce service by MPU on February 13th, 2015, opened new possibilities for customers to effortlessly buy services and products online using MPU Cards. Also, it utilizes the MPU E-commerce Service to settle your income taxes conveniently. On top of that, Consumers can seamlessly make payments through the online payment system with MPU cards. If the MPU card holders want to make use of the E-commerce service, they have the choice to contact one of the desired banks from the list of banks that offer the service. The E commerce member bank list is as follows:

- 1.Ayeyarwady Bank Public Company Limited (AYA)
- 2.Kanbawza Bank Limited (KBZ)
- 3.Co-operative Bank Public Company Limited (CB)
- 4.Myanmar Economic Bank (MEB)
- 5.Myanmar Oriental Bank Limited (MOB)
- 6.SME-Development Bank Limited
- 7.Myanmar Citizen Bank Limited (MCB)
- 8.Myanmar Foreign Trade Bank Limited (MFTB)
- 9.Asia Green Development Bank Limited (AGD)
- 10.Myawaddy Bank Limited (MWD)

11. Myanmar Investment and Commercial Bank Limited (MICB)
12. Myanma Tourism Bank Limited (MTB)
13. Nay Pyi Taw Development Bank Limited (NDB)
14. Construction, Housing & Infrastructure Development Bank Public Company Limited (CHID)
15. FDB Bank Limited
16. Shwe Bank Limited
17. Yangon City Bank Limited (YCB)
18. Yoma Bank Limited (YOMA)
19. Myanmar Apex Bank Limited (MAB)
20. Global Treasure Bank Limited (GTB)
21. A Bank Limited

3.5 Myanmar Payment Union Card Registration

There are two main ways to register. The first method is to head over to www.myanmarpaymentunion.com and complete the Online Enrolment Form for a hassle-free application process. Applicants are required to provide the identical personal email and phone details that were used when creating a card at the bank. Access to the E-commerce Registration will be granted by the respective banks within a period of 3 to 5 business days after the application has been submitted. If there are any changes to the user information, it is important to inform the nearest branch of the relevant bank before submitting your application online. The second method is to ask the bank to register the MPU E-Commerce service after receiving the MPU card. Some banks prohibit registration from MPU website to gain more information needed from users, or to provide more customized seamless services while the customers use the MPU cards.

3.6 Inter Bank Fund Transfer

"IBFT (Inter Bank Fund Transfer)" means between two different banks; It is an easy and fast account transfer between MPU Card Account (or Bank Account) at any time using an ATM machine. In the past, MPU card users were able to withdraw money from ATM machines (ATM Withdrawal). Account transfer between accounts of the same bank and were only able to provide services such as changing the PIN number. Currently, MPU Card holders can use the new

technology IBFT (Inter Bank Fund Transfer) service to transfer funds between different two banks through ATM machines. No need to wait until the bank opens; no need to go to the bank anymore.

You can transfer your transactions between IBFT member banks using MPU Logo ATM cards at any time. When using the IBFT service, the service fee is a flat fee of 200 kyats and only 0.05% of the amount to be transferred, and the maximum amount of money can be transferred up to ten million kyats per day. It is very similar to Cryptocurrency Cross-chain swaps. Cross-chain swap is a mechanism for trading a token issued on one blockchain with a token issued by a different chain.[4]

3.7. MMQR and 2030 Goal

In 2025 MPU introduce Myanmar QR (MMQR) which is standardized for all digital wallets. By achieving this one QR can provide all kinds of digital wallet. The major digital wallet services follow the standard, and now MMQR is becoming an important technology that will significantly speed up the transaction processes when fully adopted with all digital wallets in the future. MPU 2030 Goal due to its milestone is to develop the digital economy and implement the interoperability platform to connect banks and nonbanks financial institutions. On top of that MPU aim to implement cross-border payment between Asia-Pacific Network (APN) member countries.

3.8. MPU Card

MPU Cards can use at merchants (shops) with MPU Logo branding and can also make card payments with international cards like JCB/UPI. When paying with MPU Cards, you can pay in Myanmar Kyats, and if you use JCB, UPI co-brand cards, you can pay in USD (or) Myanmar Kyats according to the card holder's choice. For those using MPU card at the POS, a minimum of one thousand kyat to a maximum of fifty thousand kyats can be used per day. Merchants who want to install a POS machine to accept card payments in their shops/businesses which can obtain Membership Forms through member banks that have POS service and can easily communicate according to the procedures of the respective banks. Those Merchants are required to open a Settlement Account in any of the relevant member banks to accept payments. Also, to have a good Wi-Fi or internet connections to use the POS devices. Later, POS devices that can be used with SIM cards are also available.

Some MPU cards are integrated into VISA services that are called MPU VISA card. These cards offer Tap-to-Pay service (No PIN required) at POS devices, providing more seamless experiences. These are more widely more accepted by online services globally.

At any ATM Cards with MPU logo issued by MPU member banks and can also withdraw cash with international cards like JCB, UPI. The amount that can be used is that MPU card holders can withdraw the once time for five hundred thousand kyats and the maximum limits to two million for a week. Those who want to use an ATM card can apply at their preferred MPU member banks. According to the consensus decision of all MPU member banks, the Interchange fee for cash withdrawals (Off-Us) at the ATMs of other member bank branches will be charged from 0.5% in 2022. Please be informed that starting from December 1st, the fee will be changed to 1%.

IV. Results and Discussion

4.1 The rise of MPU

Figure 1: Number of ATM, POS and Cards

There was a 26 times increasement from 710 in 2012-13 to 18,500 in 2018-19 in the number of Point of Sales (POSs). Additionally, Number of ATMs massively rose from 210 in 2012-13 to 3500 in 2018-19. On top of that, the number of registered MPU cards reached 8 million in 2018-19.

4.2 The Statistical Improvements

Figure 2: Numbers of ATM Transaction

Figure 3: Volume of ATM Transaction

Both total number of ATM Transaction and Volume of ATM Transaction jumped nearly 10 times from 2012-13 to 2013-2014. From 2017-18 to 2018-19, Both of ATM Transaction number and ATM Transaction volume rose to double. There was no downtrend in these two graphs, showing that MPU card usage is popular among the citizens.

Figure 4: Numbers of POS Transaction

Figure 5: Volume of POS Transaction

POS Transaction charts differ from ATM Transaction charts. There was four times increasement in both number of POS transaction and Volume of POS transaction from 2016-17 to 2017-18. From 2017-18 to 2018-19, Both the number of POS transactions and Volume of POS transactions increased double as same as the ATM graphs.

Figure 6: Numbers of Ecommerce Transaction

Figure 7: Volume of Ecommerce Transaction

On the other hand, Numbers of Ecommerce Transaction increased year by year from 2015-16 to 2018-19, while Volume of Ecommerce Transactions showed some downtrends in 2016-17 and 2017-18 before sharply increasing 10 times in 2018-19.[5]

4.3 A Card for All Services

Once the MPU card is registered for the E-commerce services, it is more advanced digitally. Physically, MPU card can be used at any ATM all around the country.

Small fees are charged, but the amount is negligible compared to the seamless service provided by the MPU. It can also be used to purchase at any MPU standardized POS by scanning at the POS device and entering the password.

One card is enough for buying a can of coke to mobile phones and other expensive products. Based on the user behaviour and usage pattern, two types of cards are available, namely, debit card and the credit card. Credit card is suitable for the one who does transactions at both POS and online. They provide a loan credit for card owners, avoiding directing deduction from bank balance. That provide a layer of security. Also, exclusive promotions are available for the credit card users. On the other hand, debit card is available for the one who only saves a small amount of money, and do not want to give any interests and extra service charges for the credit card. The transactions are added and deducted directly to the bank account.

Digitally, both credit card and debit card are available for powerful. First, they can be used to top-up any mobile wallet with a small charge in a blink of an eye. This also provide a form of interbank fund transfer when it comes to transactions between two major banks. It is cheaper and faster to top up from a Aya MPU card to KBZ pay for small transactions. After the cash is deposited on the KBZ pay account, the user can easily transfer to the linked bank account with free of charge. For example, 3 lakhs MMK transfer is charged 2000MMK with Interbank Transfer while MPU Top-up only charge around 1500MMK. MPU can now link with services like Grab, FoodPanda and other in-app payments for more seamless user experience. They provide all the daily activities transaction and expected to be more accepted globally with our country's growing technological advancements in banking sector. [6]

4.4 One Digital Wallet for All

Digital wallet is like having an ATM card on the smartphone. The major advantage of digital wallet is they can now transfer money from wallet to wallet within a second. This is only the few thing that MPU card are not capable of. It also exempts transaction fees that are charged on mobile banking apps. Additionally, there is no monthly or annual fees for digital wallets, which are inevitable in MPU cards. Digital wallets are also free from account closure unlike mobile banking apps even if they are not used for a long time.

Everyone can have digital wallet even if they do not have any bank account. Withdrawing money is also seamless. Digital wallet agents are available in most of the places and stores. On top of that, ATMs Provides digital wallet withdraw services, matching the functionality of a MPU card. Depositing money is straightforward. Both agents and banks provide depositing money. Cash-in from credit card and debit card are available too. Cash-in and Cash-out can even be done with peer-to-peer services. Recently, Banks introduced Digital Fixed Deposit service that allows customers to open fixed deposit account in Mobile Banking apps. So, Digital wallets stand as the major economic drivers for daily transactions for both online and offline.[7]

4.5 Banking with IBFT is now available on our devices

All kinds of businesses are co-existing and cooperating with banking services. As the and smartphones are becoming personal digital assistant devices, the banking services are also digitalized with the growing demand. The post covid lifestyle pushed the digital banking sectors a huge step forward to the more advanced future. The banking apps are now capable of providing all the necessary services from one app. With the help of interbank fund transfer, users are more convenient to use banking. For very large transactions above 10 million MMK, the interbank transfer fee is negligible. It is cheaper than taxi fee that is needed to take a ride to the bank.

And using interbank fund transfer services is more logical rather than carrying cash from one bank to another due to safety reasons. The weather is not a barrier when banking services can be done from home in one app. Also, the feature is helpful for the elder people and workaholics who cannot give time at the queue of the banks. Saving is manageable digitally, with the function that can open fixed deposit from an apps. Aya digital fixed deposit and KBZ online open term are good examples of online saving services. Banking is now accessible from all parts of the world. The people in rural areas can now manage and watch the balances in real time. Services including Western Union, Thunes, Tranglo, Ria, Merchantrades, DeeMoney provide very convenient inward global money transfer for both senders and receivers.

Applications such as KPlus, APG and Hana EZ can also be used. On top of that, SWIFT provides both inward and outward Telegraphic Transfer.

In terms of transferable network, Ria provides 169 transferable countries, including Malaysia, Japan, and Oman. For example, the workers from Japan and Korea are now transfer their salaries directly to their parents banking accounts or digital wallets, and parents can easily manage the transferred fund at their home.[8]

V. Limitations

5.1 Scams and Imperfect Counter Measure

All the newly launched services have their own compromises when they come to expose the public audience. As the digital payment and mobile banking are widely accepted, and used by most of the citizens, the scams and misuses of new technologies also emerged. The first type of scam is accessing Mobile Wallet without permission by using social engineering methods. The scammer pretends to be a responsible staff from an official bank and ask for user personal information. In this case, the method used is so simple. The scammer only must search the victim phone number by just typing in the mobile wallet's transfer tab. If the account is active, they start calling the targeted customers. After having some conversation on the line, they will start asking for user personal information, gaslighting that the information like OTP and Password are needed for updating consumers mobile wallet account. On top of that, they also warn about the consequences of privacy risks if the user does not cooperate with them for security updates. The method is also used after the customers phone is stolen. The criminals who stole the device can access to the OTP because they have the SIM card linked to the victim's mobile wallet. In this case, the tendency to get access to the account is higher because they only need to get the password. Additionally, the victim is also more likely to give the confidential information because he was already informed the official centre and will more easily believe that the scammer's call was the official one, that is serving to help him to get access to the mobile wallets again. The second type of scam is transfer-to-gain methods. In this method, the scammer first transfers the money to the victim mobile wallet account, then they accuse the transactions are related the money laundering and other criminal activities. After that, they ask the user to download the spyware apps to fix the problem.

By using spyware, they gained access to the contact list of the user which will later be used to call and create social issues. To solve these intentional bad actions, the ransom money must be paid. This also happens when the user accidentally downloads the spyware apps or gives permissions to the fake websites. To alleviate these scams, Banks introduced one device policy, meaning user can only use mobile wallet in one authenticated device. If the user needs to change the device, the permission to log in must be given from the old device, and the account will be logout automatically on the old device. This method tends to solve the problem, but the user now must go to the bank with official documents to unlock the device authentication lock, and use the account on new devices, if the old account is lost or stolen. The scam rate is also rising, so the new counter measure approach is not successful. The mobile banking apps are more secure but are not designed for daily usage like digital wallets, also they are not immune to scam and spyware attacks. [9]

5.2 Lower Implementation rate

MPU cards are widely accepted and can be used at any ATM to withdraw cash. With small transaction fees, the user can withdraw cash at other ATM. Also, MPU cards can use in all POS, powered by MPU services. But MMQR and mobile wallets are not widely available and adopted to use for transaction. The research shows that not all POS, and stores are using MPU standard MMQR, meaning that they are using proprietary QR that only works with same mobile wallets. In particular, the data showed that KBZ pay and Wave pay monopolized most of the mobile wallet transactions.

In rural areas, the other competitor's mobile wallets like Aya pay and CB pay are not used due to very few or lack of service providers. The POS will not follow the MMQR standard and will only use KBZ pay and wave pay that are convenient for most of the customers. To add on, the profit gained from the small numbers of customers who use other payment is negligible. Although the government is encouraging POS to use MMQR, there is no enforcement or regulation to standardize all the QR payment system. In contrast, there is no promotion in MMQR fees or tax reduction for the one who follows the standard. So, the payment system of the small city, and rural remains the same.

On the other hand, although several mobile banking applications are advanced with new features, customers still prefer to use traditional banking services provided by official staffs inside the physical banks.

Most of the customers are older generations that are financially more stable and have more capital than youths. In contrast, they are not familiar with the technology. Some of the people worry about making mistakes in using mobile banking apps, whereas others still prefer the emotional safety, and customized one-to-one additional explanations that is available only at the bank. This statement is also true to MPU card usage. Although MPU cards are accepted and accessible at any ATM, older generations have technical difficulties when they withdraw money at ATM. So, the banks need to consider that factors to provide more seamless services for older customers, while maintaining the safety and privacy of the users.

The last limitation is none other than payments related to transportation in Cities. Although digital payments usage alleviates the lack of small change, most taxi drivers and Mini-Oway drivers prefer cash. Additionally, transportation taxes of highway road can only be paid in cash. Even Yangon-Mandalay Expressway's toll gates are not accepting digital payments. Another problem is Yangon Bus System Cards (YBS cards). These cards are designed to provide convenient effortless service when people use public bus transportation at Yangon City. But cards cannot be top-upped by most of the Banking apps, MPU cards and mobile wallets.

In contrast, the ATM cards are not suitable for public transportation payments due to safety reasons. So, a direct method that can top-up YBS card easily from digital payment services are necessary. Even though YPS counters and AYA xCounters accept digital payment services, it is not straightforward to Top-up from an app anytime, anywhere.[10]

VI. Conclusions

In conclusion, the financial sector is rapidly modernized with the help of MPU standardization. From E-commerce services to the recently introduced MMQR, MPU provide a strong framework and foundation for every business and banking services, providing remarkably great user experience to the customers. In recent years, MPU became the backbone of online businesses, digital transactions and customer's essential banking services.

At the age of Artificial Intelligence and Automation, will help payment systems to move one step forward both digitally and physically with the help of faster internet, better infrastructure and more advanced technologies. Despite some limitations and technical difficulties, MPU's 2030 goal will integrate Myanmar banking sector to the globalized system by utilizing the best technological enhancements and practical standardized solutions.

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